

ATTITUDE OF TEACHERS AND STUDENTS TOWARDS TEACHING AND LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

The study was conducted to analyze the attitudes of teachers and students towards teaching and learning foreign languages. It was aimed to see how attitude affected the different aspects of development of a student's ability to learn a foreign language and how teaching is affected by teacher's attitude towards teaching foreign languages. The sample comprised 150 students and 10 teachers. The study suggests that the teachers who show positive attitude are motivated and more confident in delivering instructions in the classroom settings and use various instructional methods to deliver instructions. On the hand the students who exhibit positive attitude towards learning a foreign language show keen interest in learning a foreign language and are aware of the benefits and importance of learning a foreign language.

Keywords: *Attitude, Teaching Learning Process, Foreign Language*

Attitude

The word attitude (from Latin aptus) is defined within the framework of social psychology as a subjective or mental preparation for action. It defines outward and visible postures and human beliefs. Attitudes determine what each individual will see, hear, think and do they are rooted in experience and do not become automatic routine conduct.

Jung (1921) defined attitude as a readiness of the psyche to act or react in a certain way. The main (but not only) attitude dualities that Jung defined are: Consciousness and the unconsciousness; Extraversion and introversion; Rational and irrational attitudes and

Individual and social attitudes. Allport (1935) defined attitude as a mental or neural state of readiness, organized through experiences, exerting a directive or dynamic influence upon a individual's response to all the objects with which it is related.

From the analysis of above definitions one can conclude that attitude is dynamic in nature, it changes with time and experience. The behavior of the student towards learning depicts their prevalent attitude towards it as attitude shows us a composite picture of one's mind. Attitude of the student may vary from time to time as it depends on the environment in the school/institute. The general learning environment includes four variables which are important to consider while evaluating the attitude of teachers towards teaching and of students towards learning. These are: Attitude towards subject; Attitude towards teacher/students; Attitude towards school/institute and Attitude towards learning.

Foreign Language

A foreign language is a language indigenous to another country. It is also a language not spoken in the native country of the person referred to, i.e. an English speaker living in Japan can say that Japanese is a foreign language to him or her. These two characterisations do not exhaust the possible definitions, however, and the label is occasionally applied in ways that are variously misleading or factually inaccurate.

Some children learn more than one language from birth or from a very young age: they are bilingual or multilingual. These children can be said to have two, three or more mother tongues: neither language is foreign to that child, even if one language is a foreign language for the vast majority of people in the child's birth country. For example, a child learning English from her English father and Japanese at school in Japan can speak both English and Japanese, but neither is a foreign language to her.

People need to learn a second language because of-Globalisation; Trade; Tourism; International relations between governments; Technology and Media; and science.

History of Foreign Language Education

Although the need to learn foreign languages is almost as old as human history itself, the origins of modern language education are in the study and teaching of Latin in the 17th century. Latin had for many centuries been the dominant language of education, commerce, religion, and government in much of the Western world, but it was displaced by French, Italian, and English by the end of the 16th century. John Amos Comenius was one of many

people who tried to reverse this trend. He composed a complete course for learning Latin, covering the entire school curriculum, culminating in his *Opera Didactica Omnia*, 1657.

Innovation in foreign language teaching began in the 19th century and became very rapid in the 20th century. It led to a number of different and sometimes conflicting methods, each trying to be a major improvement over the previous or contemporary methods.

Academic Benefits of Foreign Language Learning

Studies show that learning another language enhances the academic skills of students by increasing their abilities in reading, writing, and mathematics. Studies of bilingual children made by child development scholars and linguists consistently show that these children grasp linguistic concepts such as words having several meanings faster and earlier than their monolingual counterparts. Everyone knows that reading skills are transferable from one language to another, but there are other benefits.

A 1994 report on the impact of magnet schools in the Kansas City Public Schools showed that students in the foreign language magnet schools had boosted achievement significantly (Eaton, 1994). It claimed that students in the language magnet's first kindergarten, starting in the program in 1988, had surpassed national averages in all subjects by the time they reached fifth grade. Oddly enough, the foreign language students performed especially well in mathematics. Nancy Rhodes, secretary of the Network for Early Language Learning, an organization that advocates foreign language study, points to research among third and fourth graders in Louisiana. Those who studied French scored higher in English testing than students in the control group who did not.

Attitude Towards Foreign Languages: A Research Review

Peal and Lambert (1962) found a relation among bilingualism and intelligence. The study conducted by them compares measures of verbal and nonverbal intelligence, as well as student attitudes toward French and English communities. An analysis of a subgroup of the sample, matched on socioeconomic status, shows that the bilingual students scored significantly higher than monolingual students in positive attitudes toward English speakers. **Riestra and Johnson (1964) studied changes in Attitudes of Elementary-School Pupils toward Foreign-Speaking Pupils resulting from The Study of A Foreign Language.** The experimental group had significantly more positive attitudes toward the

Spanish-speaking peoples they had studied about than did the group that had not studied Spanish.

Gardner and Lambert (1972) conducted a Meta-Analysis of Studies on Attitudes, Motivation, and Foreign Language Learning. This meta-analysis investigates the relationship of second language achievement to five attitude/motivation variables from R. C. Gardner's socio-educational model: integrativeness, attitudes toward the learning situation, motivation, integrative orientation, and instrumental orientation. The results clearly demonstrate that the correlations between achievement and motivation are uniformly higher than those between achievement and integrativeness, attitudes toward the learning situation, integrative orientation, or instrumental orientation, and that the best estimates of the population correlations are greater than zero.

Prospective foreign language teachers enter the methods class with many preconceived ideas about how languages are learned and how they should be taught. These beliefs can directly interfere with their understanding of and receptivity to the information and techniques presented in the methods class. It is suggested that a systematic assessment of student beliefs would increase student learning and satisfaction in the foreign language methods class (Horwitz, 1985).

Wiley (1985) found a correlation between high school foreign language study and higher academic performance at the college level. He examined the correlation between high school foreign language study and success in college. He found that those who studied Latin, French, German, or Spanish in high school may be expected to perform better academically in college than students of equal academic ability who do not take a foreign language. Ushida (1985) reported that students' motivation and attitude towards second language were relatively positive and stable.

Oxford and Crookall (1989) conducted a research on Language Learning Strategies: Methods, Findings, and Instructional Issues. Learning strategies are steps taken by the learner to aid the acquisition, storage, and retrieval of information. Strategies are referred to as learning techniques, behaviours, or actions; or learning-to-learn, problem-solving, or study skills. No matter what they are called, strategies can make learning more efficient and effective. The purpose of this study was to survey research on language learning strategies (LLSs), the behaviours used by learners to move toward proficiency or competence in a

second or foreign language. LLSs are useful in both formal, academic settings and informal, non academic environments—that is, for both learning and acquisition.

These studies suggest that bilingual children integrate and organize the information of two languages and thus bilingualism create advantages in terms of cognitive abilities (including memory). Bilingual students also scored significantly higher than monolingual students in positive attitudes towards Foreign Languages. Speaking a foreign language is a skill which also helps in higher cognitive abilities and also helps in increasing the confidence level of the speaker. An individual who speaks a foreign language also shows positive attitude towards the people as well as the country where that foreign language is spoken as a native language.

Aims of the Study

The study was carried out with following aims:

- To identify various schools/institutes teaching foreign languages in Chandigarh and Mohali.
- To survey the existing strategies/methods used to teach foreign languages.
- To assess the attitudes of teachers/instructors and students towards teaching and learning foreign languages.
- To know about the various advantages of learning a foreign languages.

Sample

In the present study, a convenient sample of 150 students and 10 teachers was selected from Three Schools and Two Institutes of Chandigarh and Mohali offering Russian, French and German languages.

Tools Used

Two different questionnaires suitable for collecting data from two different sections of sample i.e. students and teachers were prepared. Questionnaire meant for students was named as Form – A while for teachers was named as Form – B.

Description of Student's Survey Questionnaire (Form - A)

There were 20 questions in this form. Question No. 1- 18 had 4 options while Question No. 19 and 20 had 5 options. Students were required to tick just one option which

was most relevant according to their best of knowledge. Question No 1 – 18 were meant to gather information from students regarding their understanding of the language they are learning in terms of its importance, benefits and their attitude towards learning this language. It also gathered information about whether they are interested to pursue this language in future and are they aware of their strengths and weaknesses in learning the language. Question No. 19 was meant to analyse their attitude towards the teaching methodologies which are currently being used to teach them and what changes do they want so that their learning can be enhanced. Question No. 20 was meant to analyse their overall attitude towards the whole learning experience which they feel currently while learning this language.

Description of Teachers Survey Questionnaire (Form - B)

There were 35 questions in this form. Question No. 1- 2 had 3 options, Question No. 4 - 34 had 4 options and Question No. 35 had 5 options. Teachers were required to tick just one option which was most relevant according to their best of knowledge. Question No 1 – 32 were meant to gather information from teachers regarding their understanding of their subject's content, various methodologies used, technologies currently present and being used in foreign language teaching, kind of support they give and use for teaching, various methods which they use, etc. Question No. 33 to 35 were meant to analyse the various teaching strategies, approaches and methods which they currently use in practice while teaching a foreign language and according to them which stage is considered as most appropriate for a student to start learning a foreign language.

Statistical Techniques Employed

Analysis of data was done separately for the Students Form-A and Teachers Form-B. The frequencies of the responses were calculated to further compute the percentages responses of all the questions.

Results and its Discussion

The data was analyzed keeping in mind the aims of the study. Table 1 through 8 presents the results.

Existing Strategies/Methods used to teach Foreign Languages

To survey the existing strategies/methods used to teach foreign languages, based on teacher’s responses to find out the various strategies, methods, approaches, techniques and ways which they currently practice while teaching. These are being present vide Table-I

Table-1: Percentage-Wise Analysis of the Responses of Items for finding out Strategies/Methods used by the Teachers

S. No	Items	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1	I use varied instructional practices in my classroom.	100%	00%	0%	00%
2.	I take students’ prior knowledge into account when planning curriculum and instruction.	80%	20%	00%	00%
3.	I make connections between foreign language and other disciplines.	70%	30%	00%	00%
4.	I listen /ask questions as students work to gauge their understanding of concepts.	90%	10%	00%	00%
5.	I allow students to work in partners and pairs on homework activities for grammar.	70%	30%	00%	00%
6.	I allow students to work in partners on homework activities for reading.	80%	20%	00%	00%
7.	I provide flexible groupings for students as part of my instruction.	50%	50%	00%	00%
8.	I use technology to support my classroom instruction.	70%	20%	10%	00%

Discussion based on Table-I

On analysis, it was observed that following teaching strategies/methods were being used by the teachers to teach foreign languages:

- 90% of the teachers encouraged the students to ask questions in the target language and also themselves ask questions from the students in the same way. This encouraged the students to speak the target language in the classroom settings and also helped them in removing their hesitation.
- All the teachers used varied instructional practices in their classrooms that include audio/visual aids, internet, etc. This helped in better teaching learning process.

- 80% of the teachers took prior knowledge of the students into account as it helped the teachers to plan their instructions and curriculum accordingly.
- Around 70% of the teachers made connections between foreign languages and other disciplines as by doing this the students got a clear understanding of the subject curriculum and could relate to various situations. This practice made the learning easier.
- More than 70% of the teachers ask the students to work in groups/pairs for homework activities for grammar and reading. This helped the students not only to work as a group but also helped them to interact with each other in the target language thus provided opportunities to practice foreign language even outside their classroom settings.

Table-2: Percentage-Wise Analysis of Various Assessment Practices used by the Teachers

S. No	Which assessment practices do you use?		
i.	Pre-Assessment:	Often	50%
		Sometimes	30%
		Rarely	00%
		Never	20%
ii.	Exercises provided by books:	Often	90%
		Sometimes	00%
		Rarely	10%
		Never	00%
iii.	Project-Based Learning:	Often	30%
		Sometimes	60%
		Rarely	00%
		Never	10%
iv.	Teacher-Created Assessments:	Often	90%
		Sometimes	10%
		Rarely	00%
		Never	00%

Discussion based on Table-2

Based on Table-2, it was observed that following assessment practices are being used by the teachers:

- *Pre-Assessment*: While 50% of the teachers often used the method of pre-assessment, 30% used it only at times but 20% of the teachers had never used this assessment practice. This showed that there was a mixed opinion on the usage and the benefits of this assessment practice. Teachers who used pre-assessment felt that pre-assessment helped in getting an understanding about student’s previous knowledge and as a result curriculum and instructional practices could be developed and reformed accordingly.
- *Exercises Provided by Books*: It was a widely used method as the books provided relevant questions and exercises for practice according to the taught subject material. 90% of the teachers often used the method of assessing by exercises provided by the books.
- *Project Based Learning*: Project Based Learning helped the students to work in pairs/groups and thus it acted as a motivating factor to increase their level of interest for learning a foreign language. This practice was being often used by 30% of the teachers while 60% used this sometimes and 10% admitted to have never used it.
- *Teacher Created Assessments*: Teachers favoured Teachers Created Assessments because these assessments could be easily prepared by the teachers themselves by taking care of student’s level of knowledge and understanding. 90% of the teachers used this assessment practice.

Table-3: Percentage-Wise Analysis of Various Skills Assessed by the Teachers using Different Assessment Practices

In utilizing the above assessments, I assess the following skills:	
Listening (Interpretive)	90%
Speaking (Interpersonal, Presentational)	100%
Reading (Interpretive)	90%
Writing (Interpersonal, Presentational)	100%

Discussion based on Table-3

From Table-3, it was observed that various methods of assessments used by the teachers are utilized to assess the skills learnt by the students:

- All the teachers used various assessments to assess the spoken and writing skills of the students. These were the basic skills which helped the teachers to know about the levels of understanding achieved by the students. It also helped them in

developing curriculum and reforming their instructional methods so that teaching learning process could be made more effective.

- After spoken and writing skills, teachers stressed upon assessing listening and reading skills of the students. Both reading and listening helped the students to develop a better understanding of the language which they learn. These skills assessments also helped the teachers to get an idea about the level of understanding which their students had achieved so far.

Attitudes of Teachers/Instructors and Students towards Teaching and Learning

Teacher’s Questionnaire and Student’s Questionnaire were used to survey the teacher’s and student’s responses to find out their attitudes towards teaching and learning a foreign language. The results are being present vide Table 3.III.I through Table 3.III.V.

Table-4: Percentage-Wise Analysis of the Teacher’s Teaching Experience of Foreign Languages

S. No	Item	Responses		
		10+ years	5-10 years	1-5 years
1.	For how many years have you been teaching a foreign language?	20%	00%	80%
2.	For how many years have you been teaching in this Institute?	20%	00%	80%

Discussion based on Table-4

On analysis, it was observed that only 20% of the teachers had an experience of teaching a foreign language for more than 10 years while 80% of the teachers fall under the category of 1-5 years of experience. It was interesting to find out that the teachers never switched over their jobs to another schools/institutes after they started teaching in their current school/institute.

It was also mentioned by the teachers that they were satisfied with their jobs and they enjoy their work. Also as the need of foreign language teaching in schools/institutes is felt these days as a result the demand of foreign language teachers/experts has increased. The teachers mentioned that they were well paid as a result they felt satisfied and enjoyed their

work. This satisfaction also leads to interest and positive attitude of teachers towards their teaching.

Table-5: Percentage-Wise Analysis of the Responses of Teachers of the Items Used to Assess their Attitude towards Teaching Foreign Languages

S. No	Items	Responses			
		Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1.	I am familiar with the foreign language content standards for each grade / course I teach.	90%	10%	00%	00%
2.	I am confident in my content knowledge and in my ability to use that content knowledge to deliver instruction.	90%	10%	00%	00%
3.	I use varied instructional practices in my classroom.	100%	00%	00%	00%
4.	Instruction is delivered in the target language _____% of the time.	90 – 100	75	50	25
		50%	00%	00%	00%
5.	I participate in conversations/conferences and share my ideas about the development of the foreign language curriculum and how it is taught.	70%	00%	30%	00%
6.	I take students' prior knowledge into account when planning curriculum and instruction.	80%	20%	00%	00%
7.	I develop students' listening skills in the target language.	90%	10%	00%	00%
8.	I develop students' conversational skills in the target language.	80%	10%	10%	00%
9.	I develop students' cultural understanding and proficiency in the target language.	80%	20%	00%	00%
10.	I make connections between foreign language and other disciplines.	70%	30%	00%	00%
11.	My students use the target language both within and beyond the school setting.	50%	40%	10%	00%
12.	I listen /ask questions as students work to gauge their understanding of concepts.	90%	10%	00%	00%
13.	I allow students to work in partners and pairs on homework activities for grammar.	70%	30%	00%	00%
14.	I allow students to work in partners on homework activities for reading.	80%	20%	00%	00%
15.	I encourage students' interest in foreign languages.	80%	10%	10%	00%
16.	I support and encourage the use of emerging technologies in foreign	80%	20%	00%	00%

	language instruction.				
17.	I provide flexible groupings for students as part of my instruction.	50%	50%	00%	00%
18.	I provide parents with strategies to support the learning of their child.	10%	00%	50%	0%
19.	I feel confident delivering foreign language instruction for the levels I teach.	80%	20%	00%	00%
20.	The curriculum used in my institute is clearly articulated and executable.	80%	20%	00%	40%
21.	Sufficient time is allocated for foreign language instruction at my level.	80%	10%	10%	00%
22.	I have ready access to technology to support my instruction.	90%	10%	00%	00%
23.	I use technology to support my classroom instruction.	70%	20%	10%	00%
24.	I am confident in differentiating instruction for students needing additional support.	70%	10%	20%	00%
25.	I am confident differentiating instruction for students needing more challenging work.	80%	10%	10%	00%
26.	I feel I have a clear understanding of my individual students' conceptual understanding of the foreign language.	70%	20%	10%	00%
27.	There are sufficient support systems in place for students having difficulty learning foreign languages.	80%	10%	10%	00%
28.	The institute supplies me with the professional development I need to improve my foreign language teaching skills.	90%	00%	10%	00%
29.	I receive useful feedback on my foreign language instruction from my Principal /Supervisor.	50%	10%	40%	00%
30.	I use the data from assessments to inform and reformat my classroom instruction.	70%	30%	00%	00%

Discussion based on Table-5

After analyzing the data responses the following attitude was found to be shown by the teachers towards teaching a foreign language:

- All the teachers were familiar with the standards content for each grade/course which they taught and were also confident about their knowledge and ability to deliver the instructions to the students. Every teacher took prior knowledge of the target students into account while developing and planning curriculum as well as instruction. They

also used various instructional practices like audio/visual aids, language labs, internet, etc. This reveals that the teachers take keen interest in teaching and are open towards trying various technologies and methods for teaching a foreign language.

- A mix response was observed from the teachers on delivering the instructions in the target language in a foreign language classroom. 50% of the teachers felt that the entire instructions in the classroom should be given in the target language only while the other half of the teachers who were surveyed felt that only 75% of the target language should be used in the classroom while delivering instructions.
- 70% of the teachers actively participated in various conversations/conferences and shared their ideas and thoughts with others about developing content for foreign language curriculum and the methods, procedures and strategies to be used for delivering instructions in the classroom. Though it was found that all the teachers stressed on developing listening skills, conversational skills and on developing cultural understanding and proficiency in the target language but more focus was given to the listening domain. Teachers believed that by listening, students develop a better understanding of the language and their vocabulary is also increased as well as their pronunciation is improved.
- 90% of the teachers felt that their students get opportunities to use the target language even outside the classroom settings. Students by usage of internet could interact with the native speakers in their language to enhance their skills and could also interact with each other to practice.
- Also it was observed that 90% of the teachers encouraged interest of the students in foreign languages by providing them information about the benefits and importance of learning it. This encourages and motivates the students towards learning the language as a result teaching learning process is improved.
- All the teachers supported and encouraged the use of emerging technologies in foreign language instructions and provided opportunities to the students to work in flexible settings as part of their instruction delivering strategies.
- Only 10% of the teachers who were surveyed practiced the use of providing parents with various strategies to support their child's learning. 50% of the total teacher's population did not make use of this technique; while 40% support this method but felt that they do not have any opportunities to practice this approach as in institutes

students themselves voluntarily came to learn and were usually adults. They felt that this practice could only be exercised in school settings.

- All the teachers were confident in delivering foreign language instructions for the various levels which they taught and felt that the curriculum which they followed was clearly articulated and executable. They all added that they had ready access to various technological support systems to support their instructions, but only 90% of them utilised it to the optimum level. The use of audio visual/visual aids, computers, etc. was currently put into use but due to time period restraints these technological supports were sometimes neglected.
- 90% of the teachers were confident in differentiating instructions for students who needed additional support or more challenging work and also felt that they had clear understating about individual student’s conceptual understanding of foreign language. Only 10% felt that there were no sufficient support systems available for students who had difficulties in learning foreign languages and also felt that the institutes did not provide sufficient support to them which could help improve their instructional methods.
- 60% of the teachers received useful feedback on their foreign language instructions from their Principals/Supervisors. They felt that this approach helped them to improve their instructional methods and their overall teaching performance.
- It was also observed that 90% of the teachers were satisfied with the time allotted for their teaching in the classroom. 10% of them felt that it would be better if more periods or time is provided to them. They felt that more time for practice and teaching would help the entire teaching learning process.

Table-6: Percentage-Wise Analysis of the Responses of Students of the Items Used to Assess their Attitude towards Learning Foreign Languages

S. No	Items	Responses			
		Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1.	I enjoy learning a foreign language.	76.66%	21.33%	1.33%	0.66%
2.	I understand that it is important for me to learn another language.	67.33%	29.33%	2.66%	0.66%
3.	I can have opportunities to use the language I am studying outside my class.	57.33%	30%	6%	6.66%
4.	I feel that I have learned a lot of the language I am currently studying.	54%	24.66%	20%	1.33%

5.	I feel comfortable asking questions in my foreign language class.	58.66%	40%	0.66%	0.66%
6.	I know various strategies for learning that can help me in my foreign language class.	46.66%	49.33%	3.33%	0.66%
7.	If I ever get a chance to meet a speaker of the foreign language which I learn, there are things which I could say in his/her language.	36%	50%	13.33%	0.66%
8.	I believe that knowing another language will be useful to me in my life and career.	52.66%	38%	6%	3.33%
9.	I am aware of my individual strengths and weaknesses as a foreign language learner.	36%	45.33%	16%	2.66%
10.	I plan to continue studying my foreign language at the higher levels.	56%	38%	6%	0%
11.	I would like to study another foreign language too.	38%	40%	20%	2%
12.	I believe everybody should learn a foreign language.	45.33%	45.33%	9.33%	0%
13.	Learning a foreign language also helps in understanding the culture of that country.	48%	40%	10.66%	1.33%
14.	I would like to broaden my cultural background and learn about the culture and literature of the people who speak this language.	58.66%	38.66%	2.66%	0%
15.	I would like to travel in a country where this language is spoken.	66.66%	30%	4%	0%
16.	I am actually curious about another language.	45.33%	53.33%	1.33%	0%
17.	I would like study a foreign language even if it is not a part of my curriculum.	33.33%	58%	8.66%	0%
18.	I am satisfied by the ways and methods by which I am being taught this language in my class.	55.33%	38.66%	4.66%	1.33%
19.	Mark your experiences with your foreign language course sequence on the following scale:				
	Pleasant				58%
	Somewhat Pleasant				13.33%
	Neutral				26%
	Slightly Unpleasant				2.66%
	Unpleasant				00%

Discussion based on Table-6

Table-6: reveals the attitude of the students who are currently learning foreign languages:

- 98% of the students enjoy learning a foreign language. They understand the importance of learning foreign languages and were also confident about the subject matter which they have learnt so far.
- The study reveals that only less than 2% are uncomfortable when it comes to asking questions in their classrooms and less than 4% are unaware of the strategies for learning a foreign language which could be helpful in their understanding and grasping of new information.
- 86% of the students believe that they would be comfortable to ask questions in the language which they learn if they ever come across a native speaker of that language.
- 90% of the students had a clear idea about the importance of learning a foreign language and feel that everybody should learn a foreign language. They also believed that learning a foreign language is a skill which would be useful in their entire future life as well as in their career. It also helped in understanding the culture of the country in which that language is spoken.
- The study lead to an observation according to which 97% would like to travel to the country where the language which they are learning is spoken and would like to learn more about its people, various customs, culture and their literature.
- A section of 94% of the students plan to continue their study to learn a foreign language at higher levels also and even plan to study it even if it's not part of their curriculum. Out of these students 78% were also open to learn another foreign language apart from the one which they were currently learning.
- 94% of the total students who were surveyed were pretty much satisfied by the current ways, methods, approaches and strategies which were being used in their classrooms for teaching learning practices.

Table-7: Percentage-Wise Analysis of the Changes Suggested by the Students for their Foreign Language Class

S. No	What changes would you like to see in your foreign language class?	
i.	More emphasis on speaking the language	37.33%
ii.	More emphasis on reading the language.	17.33%
iii.	More emphasis on how to learn a foreign language.	7.33%
iv.	More emphasis on the history and culture of the countries that use the	10.00%

	language	
v.	All of the above.	28.00%

Discussion based on Table-7

A few suggestions were made by the students which they would like to see in their foreign language classrooms so that the whole learning experience could be more fruitful. These suggested changes are:

- 37.33% believed that more emphasis should be given on the speaking domain while learning a foreign language. This gives an opportunity to speak and practice more and helped the learners to adjust their tongues to pronounce the words properly.
- 17.33% believed that emphasis on reading should be given as it helped to understand the concepts better and also helped in studying their course material more easily.
- 7.33% suggested that students should be oriented with the various ways, methods, strategies and techniques which could help them in learning a foreign language.
- 10% believed that history and culture should also be taught about the people and country of the target language as it would be helpful in generating interest as well as would also help in increasing curiosity among learners. This would act as a motivating factor for the learners.
- 28% of the total surveyed students were of the view point that all of the above discussed suggestions should be practiced as all of these factors are equally important and individually contribute towards learning a foreign language.

Table-8: Percentage-Wise Analysis of the Overall Student’s Experiences in their Foreign Language Class

S. No	Mark your experiences with your foreign language course sequence on the following scale:	
i.	Pleasant	58.00%
ii.	Somewhat Pleasant	13.33%
iii.	Neutral	26.00%
iv.	Slightly Unpleasant	2.66%
v.	Unpleasant	00.00%

Discussion based on Table-8

Based upon the analysis of the responses it was observed that 71% of the total surveyed students had a pleasant or somewhat pleasant experience in their classrooms while learning a foreign language while 26.00% feel that the experience was somewhat neutral. Out of the total population surveyed only 2.66% feel that the overall experience which they had so far in their foreign language class was slightly unpleasant.

Going through the various discussions, it was clear that more than 85.00% of the total population of the students who were surveyed show a positive attitude in one domain of learning or the other in their foreign language class. Less than 15% exhibit slightly negative attitude. The reason for negative attitude was due to the result of unawareness of the importance of learning a foreign language or simply lack of interest showed by the students. Also as most of the students opt for learning a foreign language voluntarily therefore it was quite clear that they were interested and curious about learning the language and therefore exhibit positive attitude towards learning a foreign language.

Various Advantages of Learning a Foreign Language

The ultimate aim of the study was to figure out the various advantages of learning a foreign language. On the basis of the analysis based upon the responses given by the students, following advantages of learning a foreign language were observed:

- Learning a foreign language improves the learners understanding of his/her native language.
- Gives an individual the ability to communicate with people s/he would otherwise not have the chance to know.
- Opens the door to other cultures and helps a student understand and appreciate people from other countries.
- Knowledge of a foreign language helps in increasing the confidence of the learner.
- Provides a school student with necessary understanding and knowledge of the foreign language required to continue study of foreign language at higher levels.
- Increases job opportunities in many careers, where knowledge of a foreign language is a real asset.

Conclusions of the Study

On the basis of the findings of the present investigation, it can be concluded that attitude has a very positive effect on both the teachers as well as the students. The study suggests that the teachers who show positive attitude are motivated and more confident in delivering instructions in the classroom settings and use various instructional methods to deliver instructions.

The students who exhibit positive attitude towards learning a foreign language show keen interest in learning a foreign language and are aware of the benefits and importance of learning a foreign language. They are aware of the various strategies and procedures which help them in learning. Moreover the students studying foreign languages of higher classes show more positive attitude as compared to the students studying in elementary or primary levels. This is due to the fact that the students of higher classes are more aware of the benefits and importance of learning a foreign language.

References

- Allport, G. W. (1935). *Attitudes in handbook of social psychology*. Massachusettes, Clark University Press
- Armstrong, P. W., & Rogers, J. D. (1997). Basic skills revisited: The effects of foreign language instruction on reading, math, and language arts. *Learning Languages*, 2(3), 20-31
- Bain, K.S, Callan.M.C,Bell.R.S,Cochran,S.M, &Sawyer.S,C(2010).Foreign language learning , aptitude, attitude, attribution, and achievement of post secondary students identified as gifted. *Journal of Advanced Academics*,22(1),130-156.
- Bamford.K,W. & Mizokawa,D.T.(1989). Cognitive and attitudinal outcomes of an additive bilingual program. Paper presented at American Educational Research Association Meeting, San Francisco.
- Bartram.B,(2012). *Attitude to modern foreign language learning*. England , The Continuum International Publishing Group Ltd.
- Breckler, S. J., & Wiggins, E. C. (1992). *On defining attitude and attitude theory: Once more with feeling*. In A. R. Pratkanis, S. J. Breckler, & A. G. Greenwald (Eds.) *Attitude Structure and Function* (407–427). Hillsdale, NJ: Erlbaum.
- Gardner, R. C. & Lambert, W. E. (1972). *Attitudes and motivation in second language learning*. Rowley, MA: Newbury House.
- Hilgard, R.E, Atkinson,R.L& Atkinson,R.C (1979). Additive-bilingual (immersion) education: Cognitive and language development. *Language Learning*, 41, 413-429.

- Horwitz, E. K. (1985), Using student beliefs about language learning and teaching in the foreign language methods course. *Foreign Language Annals*, 18, 333–340.
- James, V.M (1980). *Confronting the foreign language crisis*. New York: Continuum Publishing Corporation
- Jung, C.G. [1921] (1971). *Psychological Types*, Collected Works, Volume 6, Princeton, Princeton University Press. NJ: ISBN 0-691-01813-8.
- Kormi-Nouri, R., Moniri, S., & Nilsson, L. (2003). Episodic and semantic memory in bilingual and monolingual children. *Scandinavian Journal of Psychology*, 44(1), 47-54.
- Language use on the internet: 2000 data from Global Reach, 2009 data from World Internet Stats. GDP by language, Davis, 2004
- Nofaie ,H.AI.(2010). The attitude of teachers and students towards Arabic in EFLclassrooms in Saudi Public Schools- A case study. *Novatis- ROYAL(Research on Youth and Language)*,4(1),64-95
- Oxford.R., & Crookall.D. (1989). Language learning strategies: methods, findings, and instructional issues, *Foreign language Journal*, 10, 32-45
- Peal,E.& Lambert, W.E.(1962). The relation of bilingualism to intelligence. *Psychological Monographs*; 76(546):1-23.
- Pritchard,R.M.O.(1987). Boys and girls attitude towards French and German. *Educational Research*,29(1),65-72
- Riestra, M. A., & Johnson, C. E. (1964). Changes in attitudes of elementary-school pupils toward foreign-speaking pupils resulting from the study of a foreign language. *Journal of Experimental Education*, 33(1), 65-72. from PsycINFO database.
- Wiley (1985). High school foreign language study and college academic performance. *Classical Outlook* 62.2 : 33–36.
- Ushida,E.(2005). Students’ attitude and motivation in second language learning in online language courses.*CALICO Journal* ,23(1), 49-78.
- Wright, M.(1999).Influence on learner attitude towards foreign language and culture. *Educational Research*,41(2),197-208

Web References

- <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Language>
http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Foreign_language
<http://www.dictionary.reference.com/ Language>
<http://thesaurus.com/attitude>
<http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Language#Definitions>
<http://dictionary.reference.com/browse/language>
<http://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/attitude>